

ONLINE TEACHING AND LEARNING: BENEFITS AND LIMITATION

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Abstract:

Advancement in technology gives us a new challenge for traditional education .online teaching leaning now accepted in many environments like covid pandemic, government and academic.

This study represents explanatory information design to attained advantages and disadvantages of online learning. Result shows that the best advantage of online learning was flexibility from students perspective, now we have create new and more infrastructure to the development of online teaching for the purpose.

Key words: *online learning, blended method, Faculty, students.*

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Introduction:

Teaching is methods of transforming knowledge form one person to another like we can say this concept as mentoring, were knowledge is transfer from mentor to mentees. With dynamic nature teaching concept this concept is also changing his faces day by day. From traditional to modern and now a day's especially in this pandemic situation of covid 19 teaching concept converted in to inline teaching. Online teaching is a concept where teaching takes place with combination of internet, electricity and technology.

Advances in information technology (IT) pose new challenges for traditional higher education. universities to prepare faculty members to teach online courses with technology (e-teach). Online distance learning has attained acceptance in many work environments, mainly in the government, high-tech segments and academia. This study presents an exploratory investigation designed to identify some advantages and disadvantages of distance learning.

Objective:

- A) To find out advantages of online learning
- B) To find out disadvantages of online learning.
- C) To know understanding level of students via online mode.
- D) To find out impact of online learning.
- E) To find out Opportunity in online learning.

Significance of study:

Online Teaching provides effective alternative to real classroom teaching. Students learn best when they interact with the teachers and their peers. Students share their learning during online teaching. Generally it is observed that student become accustomed to online teaching.

Research methodology: This paper is purely based on Secondary data.

Data is collected from online article and journals.

Literature Review:

Online learning is becoming a very crucial component in many areas of our life as well as ours children and even this concept is making impact on both i.e. participants and faculties.

A) Advantages of online Learning

1) Higher Flexibility:

When both choose (i.e. Teacher and students) to continue your education online, they will have greater flexibility to juggle your career, education, and home life.

2) Save More Than a Traditional Classroom

When learning from home, instead of a traditional classroom, we will save money in a number of ways.. Not only will you save on fuel and car maintenance, but you will also save on peripheral costs, such as parking.

3) More Communication with Professor

In a traditional classroom setting, you will likely only be able to communicate one-on-one with your professor during their designated office hours, or maybe for a few minutes after class. When learning online, you will be able to communicate with your professor via email, live chat, or by phone even via social media to get the feedback.

4) Gain New Technical Skills:

Online learning will not only help you to achieve your educational goals but also can

help you gain new skills that will be beneficial when embarking on a new career. To complete your online studies, you will need to become familiar with a number of digital learning tools, [content management systems](#), collaboration tools, and basic technical troubleshooting.

5) We Will Enjoy a cross country Perspective

Online learning programs incorporate students from all across the country , as well as many students from across the globe. This will help provide for a broader range of perspectives in your online discussions and provide for better cross-cultural understanding

B) Limitations/Disadvantages:

1) *Feedback is limited*

In traditional classrooms, teachers can give students immediate face-to-face feedback. Students who are experiencing problems in the curriculum can resolve them quickly and directly either during the lecture or during the dedicated office hours.

2) E-Learning can cause social Isolation

The E-Learning methods currently practiced in education tend to make participating students undergo [contemplation, remoteness and a lack of interaction](#) Social isolation coupled with a lack of communication often leads to several mental health issues such as heightened stress, anxiety, and negative thoughts.

- Solution: Promoting increased interaction between online students.
- Utilizing blended learning environments.
- Monitoring the students for signs of social isolation.

3) Lack of communicational skill

E-Learning methods are proven highly effective at improving the academic knowledge of the students. However, developing the communicational skills of the students is an area often neglected during online lessons.

4) Cheating in online assessment: E-Learning continues to be [cheating](#) through various methods. Compared to on-campus students, online students can cheat on assessments more easily as they take assessments in their own environment and while using their personal computer.

5) Limited to certain disciplines

Not all educational disciplines are created equal and not all study fields can be effectively used in e learning. E Learning tends to be more suitable for social science and humanities, rather than scientific fields such as medical science and engineering which require a certain degree of hands-on practical experience.

6) Online learning is inaccessible to the computer illiterate population: Online learning is not giving ease to computer illiterate person and even it is not possible to make it literate immediate about digital education

C) Understanding level of students:

If we are thinking for measurement of understanding level via online, it may quite difficult for the searcher to find exact degree of understanding.

We can just measure the approx making group of students as per there age group like 5to 10. 11to15, 16 to 20 and 21to 25.

Study shown the investigation that 5to 10 age group students may understand theory subject but they are facing difficulty in technical subject like computer.

11 to 15 this age group facing difficulty in understanding they may face computer illiteracy problem while attending online learning.

16 to 20 and 21 to 25 these students may clear with the concept but not in detailed they are just having basic knowledge about the subject as university is following multiple-choice question for their exam.

Scope & Opportunities for Online Learning:

In the modern age, access to information is the key to professional success. Gone are the days when education and learning were confined to colleges and universities. E learning is a boon to people who face obstacles in getting a traditional college education. Online learning has revolutionized the knowledge economy on a global scale.

Employment Opportunities –

Quality employment generation is the positive outcome of certified online courses from reputed institutions.

Scope of Online Learning in India –

a. The main purpose of education is to achieve upward mobility

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- b. Electronic-learning through certified online courses provides a wide range of courses
- c. There is a misplaced notion, that employers prefer students with traditional brick and mortar college degrees.

Opportunities:

- 1) MBA through online learning can provide you with flexibility and help you balance your personal and professional commitments.
- 2) Big Data professionals are in great demand by top technological conglomerates.
- 3) Digital marketing is fast emerging as a top-tier career choice

As the technology has taken a greater turn in recognition, 'e-learning' method of teaching holds more importance in this age. E learning offers a few challenges and several great opportunities.

Suggestion:

This study shown that while adopting online learning there is some benefit and limitations also so we have to very careful and thoughtful while using this concept like we have to vey concentrate and strong mental background so that it not affect the our communication and mantel health. We can select the option of blended learning method.

Conclusion:

Distance learning is not new; however, it has not received respect in the academic world

Because of some of the problems presented here. Results showed that e learning allows Students and instructors work together on a course around the clock. Online learning permits educators and students to exchange ideas and information, work together on projects.

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